

VARIETIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF WHEAT PLANT SELECTION IN UZBEKISTAN.

Abdullayev Muxtorjon Bobirovich¹

a.muxtorjon2002@gmail.com

Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich²

s.f.mamarajabov@gmail.com

¹⁻²Termez Institute of Agrotechnology
and Innovative Development

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7148517>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 30th September 2022

Accepted: 03rd October 2022

Online: 05th October 2022

KEY WORDS

Wild, pubic root, protein, flour, cereal, alcohol, and starch, an ear of soft wheat, with or without a stalk.

Wheat is a group of herbaceous plants belonging to the cereal family. There are about 30 wild and cultivated species. The root system of wheat is a taproot, the main part of which develops in the soil layer, and some roots penetrate up to 180 cm deep. The stem is a stem divided into thick joints, 40-130 cm tall. Durability and productivity of wheat depends on the height of the stem. Wheat is more self-pollinating. The fruit is a grain. Depending on the size, it is divided into soft (smooth) or hard (shiny, flaky) wheat. An ear of soft wheat, with and without an ear, the ear is shorter than the ear; the grain is white or reddish, the cross-section is round, the inside is mostly flour-shaped. The ear of durum wheat is dense, the stalks grow longer and straighter than the ear. The grain is nutritious, contains protein (from 10-12% to 20-25% in selected varieties, 25-30% in wild types), starch (60-64%), fats, vitamins, enzymes, and mineral substances. Various types of

ABSTRACT

This article provides general information about the varieties, fertile species of the wheat plant in Uzbekistan, which is of great importance in the food industry, livestock and other industries.

flour, cereal, alcohol, and starch are produced from wheat grain.

Needs moisture during the spike period. Drought reduces productivity. The vegetation period of winter wheat is 45-50 days in autumn, 75-100 days in spring-summer, and 90-100 days of spring wheat. Winter wheat withstands frost up to -35°C when the snow cover is thick. Spring wheat grass can withstand frosts of -8-10°C. In irrigated regions, it is recommended to plant winter wheat on fertile land free from corn, cotton, potatoes and other field crops. It does not grow well in sour and salty soil. Sowing method: in close rows (12-15 cm between rows) or in narrow rows (7-8 cm between rows). Sowing rate - 70-110 kg per hectare in dry lands, 170-200 kg per hectare in irrigated regions, planting depth 4-6 cm ; autumn is planted deeper, the planting rate is taken 10-15% more, the seeds are sorted and treated before planting. Before planting wheat in the irrigated conditions of Uzbekistan, 10-15 t

of manure per hectare of land, 40- It is recommended to apply 80 kg of phosphorus, 40-100 kg of nitrogen, potassium.

Currently, 93 varieties of wheat are grown in Uzbekistan.

Wheat varieties

CENTURY

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Scientific-Research Institute of Cereal and Cereal Leguminous Plants in Irrigated Lands.

Authors of the variety: Siddikov R.I, Teshaboyev S.E.

Biological autumn. Belongs to the type Lutessens. The head is pyramidal in shape, medium in length, white in color. The grain is large, red, egg-shaped. The average weight of 1000 grains is from 40.4 to 58.0 g. Average plant height: from 80 cm to 105 cm.

Grade resistant to lodging and shedding, 5.0. Winter resistance 5.0 points. The average yield in the irrigated State variety trial plots is from 38.0 s/ha to 72.9 s/ha. The vegetation period is 185-225 days. According to the information of the

Republican grain inspection laboratory, the grade of the bread covering of the variety is 2.5 points. The amount of gluten is 25%.

Recommended for planting in all regions of our country.

VELVET 97

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Gallaorol Branch of the Scientific-Research Institute of Grains and Leguminous Plants in Irrigated Lands.

Authors of the variety: Amanov A, Siddikov R, Umirov N, Gaibullayev S, Jorayev M.

Biological spring (two seasons). Belongs to the genus Erythrosperrum. The average weight of 1000 grains is 40.0-41.3 g. The average height of the plant is 115-118 cm. The variety is resistant to lodging and shedding, 4.5 points. Drought resistance 4.5-5.0 points. Winter resistance 5.0 points. Average yield: 8.7-23.0 s/ha. The vegetation period is 189-192 days.

In the spring term, the average yield in the contest test is 7.3-14.8 s/ha, the vegetation period is 94 days. Cases of damage by agricultural diseases (rust) were not

observed in the competition test. It is recommended for planting in Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Samarkand and Surkhandarya regions of our country.

BOBUR

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Scientific-Research Institute of Cereal and Cereal Leguminous Plants in Irrigated Lands.

Authors of the variety: Siddikov R.I, Teshaboyev S.E, Tolonov R, Jalolov T, Puchkov Yu, Nabakov G, Kudryashov I, Solyarek T, Bepalova L, Fomenko N.

The head is cylindrical in shape, medium in length and density, white in color. The grain is medium-sized, red in color, oval in shape. The average weight of 1000 grains is from 41.0 to 44.5 g. The average height of the plant is 90 to 100 cm. Grade resistant to lodging and shedding, 5.0. Winter resistance 5.0 points. The vegetation period is 192-210 days. Cases of damage by agricultural diseases (rust) were not observed in the competition test. The

technological and baking quality of the variety is good.

Recommended for planting in all regions of our country.

SPRING 1

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Gallaorol Branch of the Scientific Research Institute of Grains and Leguminous Plants in Irrigated Lands.

Authors of the variety: Siddikov R, Khaitboyev A, Umirov N, Jorayev M.

Biological spring. Belongs to the genus *Grecum*. The head is cylindrical, white, medium length. The grain is medium-sized, egg-shaped, red in color. Average weight of 1000 grains is 31.4 g. The variety belongs to the group of medium-sized varieties. The average height of the plant is from 75 cm to 100 cm. The average yield is 31.4-45.3

s/ha. The average vegetation period is 96-100 days.

Regions recommended for planting: since 2013, it has been included in the State Register for spring planting in the irrigated lands of Jizzakh region.

JASMINE

Originator of the variety: Samarkand Agricultural Institute and "FARBOMA SELECT" scientific seed farm selection variety.

Authors of the variety: G.S. Gaybullayev, M.G. Usmanov, T.E. Astanakulov, N.Kh. Khalilov, I.T. Ergashev

Biological autumn. Belongs to the type Lutessens. The spike is prismatic in shape, medium in length and density, red in color. The grain is large, red, egg-shaped. The height of the plant is 75-80 cm, it is resistant to lodging, winter hardiness is 5.0 points, it is resistant to grain shedding. Average grain yield is 58.0-70.5 s/h. The growing season of the variety is 201-207 days. Cases of damage by agricultural diseases were not observed in the competition test.

It is recommended for planting in Bukhara, Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Samarkand and Surkhandarya regions of our country.

TEST 1

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Surkhandarya Branch of the Research Institute of Cereal and Cereal Leguminous Plants in Irrigated Lands.

Authors of the variety: Faizullayev I.F, Omonov A.O, Bepalova L.A.

The head is pyramidal in shape, medium in length, the grain is large, semi-oblong in shape. The average weight of 1000 grains is from 36.8 to 42.6 g. The average height of the plant is 80 to 90 cm. The variety has 4.0 points of lodging and shedding resistance,

5.0 points of winter resistance. The average yield in the irrigated State variety test plots is from 52.1 s/ha to 58.5 s/ha. The vegetation period is 183-212 days.

It is recommended for planting in Bukhara and Surkhandarya regions in our country.

TURKSTON

Originator of the variety: Selection variety of the Kashkadarya Grain Crops Selection and Seed Breeding Scientific Research Institute.

Authors of the variety: Abdullayev O, Omonov A, Ziyodullayev Z.

Biological autumn. Belongs to the genus Erythrospermum. The head is cylindrical in shape, medium in length, white in color. The grain is medium-sized, red in color. The average height of the plant is from 90 cm to 105 cm. Grade resistant to lodging and shedding, 5.0. Winter resistance 5.0 points. The average yield in the irrigated State variety trial plots is from 40.0 s/ha to 57.0 s/ha. The vegetation period is 190-230 days.

Regions recommended for planting: since 2011, it has been included in the State Register for autumn planting on irrigated lands in Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, Tashkent, Khorezm regions.

Conclusion

This article provides brief information about wheat varieties grown in Uzbekistan and their characteristics. Wheat plant is grown on a large scale all over the world - the food industry cannot be imagined without wheat. As a result of breeding achievements in Uzbekistan, more than 150 varieties and hybrids of wheat that are productive, resistant to diseases and resistant to environmental factors are now being grown on a large scale.

References:

1. Balashev N.I., Zeman G.O., Vegetables , T., 1977;
2. Abdukarimov D., Safarov T., Ostanakulov T., Dala harvest selection , breeding as well as genetics basics , T., 1989.
3. Khaitovna P.M., Faksriddinovich M.S. Technology of growing cauliflower // Texas Journal of Interdisciplinary Research. - 2022. - T . 6. - S. 8-10 .
4. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=Buztwd0AAAJ&authuser=1&citation_for_view=Buztwd0AAAAJ:u-x6o8ySG0sC
5. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=Buztwd0AAAJ&authuser=1&citation_for_view=Buztwd0AAAAJ:2osOgNQ5qMEC
6. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=Buztwd0AAAJ&authuser=1&citation_for_view=Buztwd0AAAAJ:qjMakFHDy7sC
7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7115076>